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**Sonorism and Aspects of Extra-Musicality in
Polish Music Post 1960**

The development and social significance in the
late twentieth to early twenty-first century

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(3BMus International)

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“I was born in Silesia...It is old Polish land. But there were always three cultures present: Polish, Czech, and German. The folk art, all the art, had no boundaries. These boundaries were supposed to exist, but they were shifted frequently to the right and to the left. But that did not mean that people started thinking differently.” Henryk Górecki (1997)¹

I, Ben McHugh confirm that work is my own.

Signature _____ Date _____

¹Botstein, Anne(trans.), Górecki Henryk Mikołaj, Harley, Maria Anna, 'The Twentieth Century, On Life and Music: A Semi-Serious Conversation', *The Musical Quarterly*, Vol. 82, 1, (Oxford University Press), pp.73-75.

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Schools or groups of collective artistic vision or direction can often, over time grow stale. When diverse musical languages are diluted into a single condensed ethos a certain homogenisation occurs, something that can take decades to receive development or to indeed dismiss.

However, in the case of the Polish Sonorist School of the second half of the twentieth century this problem is not immediately apparent.

The outstanding range and spectrum of the styles and influences of Polish composers born in the twentieth century could show an almost microcosmic history of Western compositional trends and styles in all their diversity.

Adrian Thomas in the introduction to his seminal masterpiece on Polish music, *Polish music since Szymanowski* (2005) mentions and labels the “Polish School” or 'Sonorism' as a range of individuality in Polish composers, post 1960.²

It is this juxtaposition of individuality of voice through diversity in style that has produced many acclaimed Polish composers.

As Henryk Górecki (1933-2010) points out above, it was precisely this mixing especially in the case of the region of Silesia (Śląsk) and diversity that helped to develop a kind of individuality in art. The intermingling of the various cultures of Czech, Polish and German contributed to multiple distinct aesthetics that were in constantly interaction with each other.

The length and breadth of styles ranging from serialism, neoclassicism and avant-garde experimentation in the styles of early Górecki and Lutosławski to the post-

²Adrian Thomas, *Polish Music since Szymanowski*, (Cambridge 2005), p. xviii.

modern and even neoromantic expressionism of late Penderecki and Kilar and the eclectic post-modern aesthetics of recent composers such as Pawel Lukaszewski can be seen as almost a full spectrum of Polish music at this time.

However, not only limited to the outside influence of Western Europe, inspiration of direct Polish heritage is also a strong point in the defining of a certain Polish style in the twentieth century. Nationalism in many forms is often seen as a possibility for composers drawing on folk motifs and religious or nationalist texts. Indeed, a full account of this would be desired in order to represent the complex sociological links that existed at that time.

In this thesis I will look at the life and works of Polish composers at the end of the 20th century, specifically Henryk Górecki, Witold Lutosławski, Andrzej Panufnik and Krzysztof Penderecki and try to define and explain stylistic traits which have lead to the title of 'The Polish composers' school' of Sonorism.

I will assess this group on its own merits and endeavour to draw connections and parallels both in the cultural and political climates of post World War II Poland. Under the same topic I will be looking at certain aesthetic and philosophical considerations and aspects of extra-musicality in the works of this period. I will also examine the political pressures and restrictions that the Polish people were subjected to, under the Soviet regime from the 1960s to the 1990s.

A special emphasis will be given to investigating composers' personal responses to these difficult topics and highlight their wider affects and significance on the Polish psyche.

I hope to use this information in order to assess how the significance of modern Polish music can be defined in the twenty-first century and examine if it is correct to identify Sonorism as solely a musical phenomenon or if there is a sufficient extra musical, social and historical basis for its evolution and musical place in the last century.

1. Beginnings of a Polish Musical Voice & the Inter-War Underground

Before embarking on the main questions of the topic, it is useful to review some of the steps that led to the development of a strong Polish voice in composition.

Certainly, it could be considered, it was the progressive aesthetic view of Karol Szymanowski (1882-1937) that helped to establish a distinct Polish musical voice previous to World War II. It was this aesthetic which was to influence so many Polish musicians and composers for decades to come.

The main developments he called for were in looking not at the legacy of German romanticism but towards mysticism, orientalism, French impressionism and modernism; Polish highlander (Górale) folk music and European medieval chant.

His love of Polish highlander music³ has particularly influenced later composers such as Henryk Górecki, Wojcieck Kilar and Tadeusz Baird⁴. His work in education and with the Pre-war Young Poland in Music (*Młoda Polska w Muzyka*) which took after the Young Poland movement in art and consisted of the composers and musicians Grzegorz Fitelberg, Ludomir Różycki and Apolinary Szeluto can be seen as one of the first strong beginnings in modern Polish expression. Indeed, he often greatly emphasised the importance of originality in Polish art.

“Given the new social-political context within Poland (Poland's long-awaited liberation from the German Empire after WWI), it seems extraordinary that, once more, Szymanowski was acting more or less alone in drawing so intensively on his native traditions. None of his near-contemporaries was half as interested in defining afresh the nature of Polishness in music.”⁵

³It is well known that he rented a summer house called 'Atma' in the town of Zakopane in the Podhale region of Southern Poland.

⁴Co-founder of the Warsaw Autumn festival with Kazimierz Serocki in 1956.

⁵Adrian Thomas, *Polish Music since Szymanowski*, (Cambridge 2005), p. 6.

Even though he was considered a minor within the musical establishment of his time, he was able to back up his views with a developmental oeuvre of works that featured many of the key stylistic tenets of the time.

Indeed, he is often considered as one of the first great Polish symphonists.

Szymanowski's aesthetic could be seen as being highly individual for his time and place. And his progressive nature was asserted in his view that Poland should create a national voice in art against all odds. And, although nationalism in music is considered to be a largely a nineteenth century phenomenon, Szymanowski's nationalism was largely in reference to a desired cultural awakening and growth in Polish art on an international stage and not a mere pushing of Polish cultural values within its own milieu.

He passed on this legacy to the next generation of inter-war composers including names that would become synonymous with Polish expression over the next few decades: Bolesław Szabelski who studied composition with Szymanowski in Warsaw(1927-29) and developed a strong neoclassical voice, and Witold Lutosławski who studied with Witold Maliszewski and was deeply influenced by Szymanowski's rhapsodic style particularly in his third symphony *Song of the Night* which Lutosławski attended a performance of in Warsaw in 1924 when he was only eleven years old.⁶

Szymanowski was certainly fortunate not to have seen the destruction which was to envelop his capital and nation in the coming years. This fate was to befall scores of other artists and composers who had to struggle under Nazi

⁶Lutosławski later commented on the impression that the experience left on him at the time, although he was to consciously move away from the opulent late romantic style of Szymanowski's work a part of him reserved and enormous respect for his predecessor.

oppression and then the Soviet persecution and political suppression that was to follow.

Cafés and make-shift theatres were to become the new concert hall and many artists and intellectuals had to earn their livings in the grimy and overcrowded establishments of underground Warsaw. It was in this atmosphere of cultural survival that the piano duo of Lutosławski and Panufnik met and began performing many of their own serious compositions and arrangements of well-known tunes for the locals.

In fact, it was around this time that Lutosławski wrote *Variations on a theme of Paganini* for two pianos (1941) and *Songs of Underground Struggle* (*Pieśni walki podziemnej*) for voice and piano (1942-44), whilst at the same time working on his *first symphony* (1941-47). The other half of the duet, Panufnik, was also busy working on his music and at this time he wrote his first two symphonies (1940 & 41) and his *Tragic Overture* for Orchestra (1942).

In contrast to many of the composers that managed to live secure enough lives despite lightning raids by the SS on performances, many were forced to flee Poland or were taken captive by the Nazis. Most composers were forced to wait it out and compose in isolation rather than induce risks of arrest through attendance of performances or cultural events

⁷Image of destroyed Warsaw during the Warsaw uprising, World War II Database, <http://ww2db.com/image.php?image_id=8632>.

2. Post war Cultural Thaw, The Warsaw Autumn and The Backgrounds to Sonorism

By the 1950s Poland was taking steps to get over the shock and devastation of the second World War. This rebuild was mostly due to the inter-war plans by Poles.

The main, and perhaps most important cultural institution at this time was the Polish Composers' Union ZKP (Związek Kompozytorów Polskich).

Formed in 1925 and operated secretly during the war, it was officially titled ZKP in 1945. With notable figures such as Perkowski, Palester, Wiechowicz and Lutosławski, it promoted the cooperation of composers and performers to help rebuild the cultural life of Warsaw. On top of this, the notable publishing house PWM (Polskie Wydawnictwo Muzyczne) was responsible for collecting and disseminating (mostly in secret) the scores of composers that were written during the war. It was at this time that composition in Poland was to reach a level of hitherto unheard-of productivity. It was these groups who were responsible for the growth of Polish music and the promotion of national culture after the second world war.

Lutosławski and Panufnik, in a largely pan-tonal aesthetic similar to Bartók in Hungary and Roussel in France, were perhaps the most responsible for Poland's cultural revival and in determining a Polish international musical voice post 1945. Their working careers spanned a great majority of the twentieth century from the early 1930s to the early to mid 1990s⁸. Stylistically though, they were quite different, despite knowing each other quite well and performing

⁸Lutosławski began composing in 1930 (Three years before the birth of Górecki and Penderecki) and finished with his death in 1994. Panufnik's first compositions can be attributed to 1934 with his last one written in 1991.

together during the war. The almost Schoenbergian atonality of Lutosławski is enhanced by the latter's use of small note cells and the abandonment of serial techniques, Panufnik's more fluid aesthetic akin to Roussel and indeed Roussel's young Czech student Bohuslav Martinů points to a more private and personal post romantic style. Panufnik's music expresses a more personal vein to Lutosławski's controlled aleatoricism, although watched closely by the Soviets⁹.

With these in mind, both Panufnik and Lutosławski found a common aesthetic in the belief that music devoid of an imposing system (albeit utilising a system developed and created for the work in question) could in fact be just as expressive, and indeed, as controlled as serialist technique, but which were more dynamic and open to change depending on the demands and aesthetic of the work¹⁰

2B. The Warsaw Autumn

After the fall of Nazi Germany, the Russian Soviet army had firmly established its base in Post-War Poland. It was not until the death of Stalin in 1953 that things began to improve both culturally and socially.

With the beginning of the Warsaw autumn festival of contemporary music in September 1956, a new era of Polish contemporary music was to begin.

Among the first performances at the premier festival were Lutosławski's *Little Suite* (1951), Szabelski's neoclassical works such as *Symphony No. 3* (1951) and *Concert Grosso* (1954) Kilar's *Little Overture* (1953) and Szymanowski's

⁹ Panufnik had travelled to many places as part of his position as vice president of the composers' union, a position which he was almost forced to take by Stalin's officers in Poland, and on trips mainly to the USSR satellite states. These conditions ultimately forced Panufnik to escape to London, and he was subsequently deleted from soviet conducting records in his native Poland.

¹⁰ The fact that either they were rebelling against the second Viennese school out of disdain for the Austro-Germanic tradition or by artistic choice remains to be said here.

infamous *third symphony* of 1916 with his *Stabat Mater* of 1926 representing earlier Polish works. Works by international composers such as Bartók, Berg, Messiaen, Schoenberg and Stravinsky were also performed.¹¹ Paradoxically, during the communist era the festival thrived¹² and despite only being cancelled twice in 1957 and 1982 it has relied since on state funds for its operation and maintenance.

This growth space for new music certainly helped to influence the younger generation of Polish composers born in the thirties. These composers who were responsible for many of the Cold War Avant-Garde developments in music already had the fortune of a major outlet for contemporary and experimental music on an international level.

¹¹Adrian Thomas, *Polish Music Since Szymanowski*, (Cambridge, 2005), Appendix 2.

¹²A brief history of the Warsaw Autumn, <<http://www.warsaw-autumn.art.pl/02/about.html>>

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3. Backgrounds to Sonorism – Górecki & Penderecki

“The youngest generation of Polish composers has plunged into the new, present-day world of music much more naturally and easily; they had no need to change their mode of thinking and feeling and to overcome any emotional and rational barriers within themselves. They did not experience the period of isolation in the years 1949-1955, and they imbibed the present time in a perfectly natural way, simply by living it. All the products of present-day culture - printed music, films, books, paintings of the most avant-garde artists - were open to them without limitations”.¹⁴

Defining sonoristic traits in the work of Polish composers is no mean feat, the mindset and cultural thaw after the death of Stalin in 1953 certainly did much to increase the general artistic freedom, and the abundance of musical activities and styles that followed increased dramatically, and many Polish composers felt less

¹³Polish Collection of the Warsaw Autumn 1956-2005 CD.

¹⁴Jarocinski, Stefan, “Polish Music after World War II”, *The Musical Quarterly*, Vol. 51, 1, Special Fiftieth Anniversary Issue: Contemporary Music in Europe: A Comprehensive Survey, (Oxford University Press 1965), pp. 244-258.

of a sense that they were being watched or monitored by the Soviet authorities. Indeed, with an increasing level of music activity many composers were awarded prizes in international competitions, including the famous example of Penderecki's triple win at a Polish competition¹⁵ in 1959.

It was this artistic freedom that greatly helped the composers Górecki and Penderecki get their works recognised at the beginning of their careers, particularly works that were to define the sonorist Polish avant-garde of the 1960s.

Before examining the work of this generation of composers it is useful to mention what constitutes a working definition of 'Sonorism' with relation to the specific techniques and ethos of this 'school'. The Oxford Dictionary of Music and Musicians explains "Sonoristics" as:

"Once described as a theory of the 'actual shape of the musical work' (Dziębowska, 1979), sonoristics involved a thorough re-evaluation of the traditional elements of music and placed the emphasis on issues of sound generation, including both electro-acoustic and non-traditional means of vocal and instrumental articulation and their dynamic differentiation, the spatio-temporal distribution of sound in the composition, and transformational processes shaping the form. In effect, sonoristic analysis approached the musical work as a dynamic entity resulting from the interaction of sonic phenomena and kinetic processes."¹⁶

and labels Sonorism as:

"Sonorism", a derivation from 'sonoristics', refers to the avant-garde style in Polish music of the 1960s that placed timbre at the centre of compositional interests."¹⁷

¹⁵ Winner of first, second and third prize at the second competition of young composers in 1959 organised by the league of Polish composers with *Psalms of David*, *Strophes* and *Emanations*. Two scores were written in his own hand, whilst the third was written in the hand of a colleague so as not to arouse the suspicion of the judges.

¹⁶ "Sonoristics, sonorism.", Grove Music Online, Oxford Music, Online, <<http://www.oxfordmusiconline.com/subscriber/article/grove/music/2061689>>, [Accessed Apr. 30, 2011].

¹⁷Ibid.

Here we can see the beginnings of a compositional focus on the sound mass principle or idea of sound colour in the shaping of a work, an interest in timbre and forms based on sounds or sound types was of high importance, levels of noise and density of pitch and tone clusters, parameters of attack, sustain and decay, and ultimately by sounds influenced by the electronic experiments of older composers such as Stockhausen and Pierre Schaeffer, Xenakis and Ligeti were the compositional focus of this time.

However, on the other hand, there is a certain power and extra-musicality associated with the sonorist idea. Not only in the avant-garde aesthetic but also in the general consciousness. Their work constituted a further move away from conventional ideas of pitch and harmony even in an era of post-Schoenbergian dodecaphony.

It also represented a look outside of pitch and at the same time inside of these as the use of scales and conventional pitch structure were almost completely non-existent.

Instead composers created atmospheres, sounds reminiscent of explosions, screams, non-harmonic sounds with complicated harmonic spectra and non-periodic sound waves, and these did much to trigger a greater response than extremely organised pitches or indeed the intentional Schoenbergian ‘emancipations of dissonance’ did earlier.

Thus, it is useful to consider the extra-musical (albiet unintentional or unconsciously created by composers) connotations of sonorism alongside its sound properties and analytical merits as part of its development and cultural reception at the time.

Ever since the beginning of his musical studies and early career, the compositional style of Krzysztof Pendercki has seemed to have been in flux and, indeed, changes of style and expression have been central to his view on twentieth century music. He was educated in Warsaw, and his work in the Polish Radio experimental studio, which was established in Warsaw in 1957, seems to have had a formidable influence on his work. He was exposed to and became familiar with the music of Stockhausen and Pierre Schaeffer, which was being broadcast out of WDR in Cologne at the time. This hugely influential studio was to define and influence the European avant-garde and progress of electronic music for the foreseeable future. Although Pendercki had never focused solely on recorded electronic music¹⁸ in the same way that Stockhausen or Pierre Schaeffer were, he found an expression in writing seemingly 'electronic' music for acoustic instruments.¹⁹

His early love of string instruments as a child culminated so to speak in his infamous *Threnody for the Victims of Hiroshima* (1959) a work that was originally to be titled 8'37" being the duration of the score measured in minutes and seconds. This work, which exhibits extended techniques specific to string instruments, harmonics, tone and microtonal clusters and movement between *sul tasto* and *sul ponticello* was (and still is) an important piece in twentieth century music.

The work can be seen as mostly textural with the most common sound textures being sound mass blocks of clusters including quarter tones and use of 'highest note possible', delicate counterpoint in the third section beginning on bar

¹⁸His oeuvre contains two pieces for instruments and tape.

¹⁹He has often mentioned that he found writing 'Tape' music too limiting in terms of performance expression and that he enjoys the unpredictability that arises with each different performance of his work.

26, staggered entries of pitches culminating in a cluster and subsequent movement of clusters up and down in space and also modulations of pitch including movement between short and wide vibrato at the distance of a quarter tone. It also exhibits the smooth filtering of sounds and pitches reminiscent to the processing of white noise in subtractive synthesis with the use of band pass filters, where frequencies are enhanced within a narrow band and at the same time frequencies outside of this are filtered out by electronic means.

In terms of expression in the score: there is increased rhythmic and dramatic freedom at the hands of the conductor for indicating entries. The durations of time are relatively fixed and silences are given to the conductor in the form of breath marks. The notation is clear and easy to follow and although he devised new symbols for the notation of extended techniques, the majority of the score is an augmentation of western notation up until this time.

“With the *Threnody*, no two performances or recordings are ever the same. It's always different. I always leave space for each musician and the imagination and creativity of the conductor, which is not always the case that they understand how to be that way.”²⁰

Overall the work exhibits a sound akin to the radio studio experiments in Cologne during this time, but it cannot be seen as electronic in itself, albeit merely influenced by Penderecki's familiarity with these sounds and sound colours. As such, the Sonoristic traits of this work are quite strong, and *Threnody* is not unique in his oeuvre, as Adrian Thomas mentions about Penderecki's work *Polymorphia* (1961) the process of composition is more sonoristic than anything else.²¹

²⁰ Penderecki in interview with Andy Battaglia for Resident Advisor Magazine (2010).

²¹ Adrian Thomas, *Polish Music Since Szymanowski*, (Cambridge 2005), p. 162.

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His attraction to sonorism is often related to his disappointments with the pontillistic techniques of the previous avant-garde and his concern with “The line” pushed him to develop his style beyond what he thought was the limited avant-

²²One of Penderecki's sketches for Polymorphia (1961).

garde and deal with such compositional and aesthetic issues as texture, sound colour and developmental form as opposed to the micro-structures, structuralism and complexity popular at that time. A freedom from neoclassicism, melody, specific pitch, tone matrices and sparse articulation helped to define his style during the early 1960s.

He can be compared with other twentieth century composers, also, by way other factors than his compositional style. The influence of painters on his work such as Paul Klee and Yves Klien in terms of form and stark abstract blocks of colour is also important. His concentration on colour in this respect can be measured, and he has mentioned the effect that architecture has had on his compositional style. This brings us back to the original quote on sonorism's definition, prizing sound colour as a sense of drama above anything else, and the overall sonoric impression being paramount to the reception of a work.

His work *Fluorescences* (1962) for large symphony orchestra can, thus, be seen as the high point of his sonorism. It contains an augmented percussion section, featuring Satie like instrumentation, which further demonstrates his philosophy of looking backwards as well as forwards (perhaps a trait that he had passed on from his early neoclassical days). He continued down the same path as *Threnody* and his experiments with notation and timbre were not exhausted. However, it was not until his *St. Luke's Passion* in 1965 that things began to change, at least consciously in, with regard to his own view of his work.

His style took on a more neoromantic aura and this is indeed a label that many musicologists have attributed to his style after this point.

As many composers do when faced with being labelled, he has reacted against the label of Sonorist. He prefers to see himself as more of an individualist in the development of a dynamic yet approachable style.

It is useful now to examine the early works of Górecki and determine their place in the music of this time. In contrast to Penderecki's upbringing Henryk Górecki's was more provincial. Raised and educated in a coal mining region in the Podhale region in Polish Silesia, he experienced a higher level of metropolitan cultural isolation than his contemporary. Indeed, his place in the Polish avant-garde was not asserted as swiftly as Penderecki's, and, although his studies with Szabelski showed neoclassical roots akin to Penderecki, it was not until a concert of his music was organised by the High School of Music in Katowice in 1958 (with Lutosławski in attendance) that he was to be recognised as a composer of merit.

In terms of works, the premier of his *Epitafium* (at the second Warsaw Autumn in 1958) paired him with composers and artists in the international arena for the first time.

If Penderecki was to show sonoristic elements through unconventional use of notation and timing in his earlier work, was Górecki to approach it in a different way, the pontillistic and klangfarbenmelodie construction of his *First Symphony* and his fiery *Scontri (Clashes)* 1960²³ scored for a custom orchestral stage layout are indeed formidable pieces. Their construction is more tightly

²³ Related in title as an antithesis to Nono's *Incontri (Meetings)*.

controlled than Penderecki's work and exhibit extended permutations of the serialism that he had used previously, although this time used in more integral ways.

Clusters and mathematical rhythmic structures akin to Lutosławski created more sonoristic works than their predecessors. In terms of sound complexity and the sheer energy of these works, Polish music had seen nothing of its ilk before. *Scontri* had its premiere at the 1960 Warsaw Autumn, and this propelled him into Polish music with a reception of combined jeers and praise.²⁴ Adrian Thomas labels it as Górecki's *Rite of Spring*.²⁵ *Scontri* is indeed a more sonoristic work than its predecessors, despite still containing serial techniques, but in a more integral way and showed the traces of the developments that were to come. Pieces such as *Genesis I: Elementi* for strings and *Genesis III: Monodramma* for solo soprano, metal percussion and six double basses, which used timbral constructions that were previously unseen before in Górecki's output, are both pieces which exhibit sonoristic traits. The score also included the use of Polish vowel sounds and harsh percussion arranged in three instrument groups which are further subdivided into Soprano, Alto, Tenor and Bass depending on the 'register' of each section of metal percussion.

Refrain (1965) was seen as Górecki's stylistically pivotal work and just as Penderecki's was regarded as *St. Luke's Passion* it seems that parallels were evident, at least superficially. The fact that they shared similar origins, and both were avid proponents of the neoclassicism inherited from their teachers and from

²⁴ Adrian Thomas, *Górecki*, (Oxford: 1997), pp. 12-38.

²⁵ Adrian Thomas, *Polish Music Since Szymanowski*, (Cambridge: 2005), p. 188.

Stravinsky's work previous evidently makes for further comparison. Indeed, the timing of their change is worth pointing out and they moved to the creation of sonoristic works, albeit in an aesthetically different way. Górecki and Penderecki's avowal of the avant-garde can be seen as their struggle against these roots and represents their awareness of developments on the other side of the Iron Curtain, something which would have been extremely difficult pre-1953. With help from the Warsaw Autumn and local agencies they were able, and culturally obliged, to put Poland on the avant-garde musical map and promote Polish culture outside of the Soviet Bloc. Because of this they can be seen as the fathers of the Polish avant-garde in the 1960s.

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tn 1-3

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²⁶The final page of Penderecki's later sonorist work *De Natura Sonoris No. 1* (1966).

4. A Change of Mind, a Change of Heart? Towards a New Romanticism

An examination of the stylistic changes in the works of Penderecki and Górecki post 1965.

“As unexpected newcomers, Polish composers had played briefly in the late 1950s and early 1960s with new idioms and technical ploys from the West before discarding or dismantling them as they sought their own path. By and large they concentrated on expressive contact with their listeners rather than investing in complex technical means.”²⁷

Stylistic change or evolution in the work of composers is always an interesting phenomenon. Composers and musicians begin studies, are exposed a varying degree of influences²⁸ and often only reach or develop their true voice much later on in their maturity when they have assimilated what they term as important and discarded what they have seen as unnecessary.

Penderecki has termed his beginning of a new work as a searching, both backwards and forwards, and his stylistic evolution reflects this.

He mentions that his *St. Luke's Passion* (1965) constitutes a stylistic turning point in his career, and the majority of the works after this exhibit religious or philosophical themes lending towards a more emotional neo-romantic style. That is, however, not to say that he discarded the new expressive techniques that he had experimented with in the late 50s and 60s, but he assimilated these techniques into his later work, and to view his shift as a complete rejection of the avant-garde is a gross over-simplification.

He often describes this aspect of his aesthetic metaphorically in the form of walking in a labyrinth, reaching a junction and wondering whether to retrace his steps or to keep going in a new direction. Rather than having a clear

²⁷Adrian Thomas, (1997), p. 69.

²⁸ Often during the period in question performance and geographically restricted or dependant on radio broadcast from the West.

compositional and developmental direction or goal he feels he has more freedom in establishing challenges and being able to draw on past styles and techniques in the pursuit of an integral work.

With *St. Luke's Passion* he was to use choirs in a similar way to the use of strings in his *Threnody*, and although the harmony and gestural content still lies within a twentieth century language, his move backwards towards the Oratorio form indeed with a Latin text and use of the B-A-C-H motif points to a classicist mindset and this is reinforced with the presence of eight symphonies, the most recent being the choral symphony *Symphony Number 8: Lieder der Vergänglichkeit (Songs of Transience)*, (2004, Rev. 2008).

“True, in his post-sonoristic output Penderecki does not completely renounce the conquests of sonorism. But even though one occasionally finds glissandi and non-traditional playing techniques in his later scores, they occur separately from their original basis: not as an indispensable means for the realization of systemic assumptions, but rather as interesting sound effects once invented and, though still remaining at the composer's disposal, already relating to a different musical world.”²⁹

In reference to his stylistic change he has confessed that he “could not continue in the style” of *Threnody* and *Polymorphia* and broadly cites this period as being from 1959 to 1970.³⁰

Many sources have cited orchestral difficulties being a substantial reason for his stylistic shift and orchestras after the war as being unsympathetic to the performance of his avant-garde works, despite Poland's orchestral scene at that time being quite liberal. Even the composer himself has had many difficulties in

²⁹ Mirka Danuta, “To Cut the Gordian Knot: The Timbre System of Krzysztof Penderecki”, *Journal of Music Theory*, Vol. 45, 2, (Yale: Duke University Press 2001), p. 453.

³⁰ Penderecki interviewed by Michael Dungan for the Castletown Concert Series, Castletown House. Recorded by the author 11 September 2010.

performance, stating that at typical performance of *Threnody* needs a minimum of two rehearsals in order to be realised, a condition which most professional orchestras are unable to provide.³¹

The abundance of extended techniques in his earlier works was important in his learning as a composer and in his testing of the waters so to speak. These early expressive devices certainly did fill a void that was absent in European music and did much to enrich the Polish musical standing, but their stylistic stagnation in the eyes of the composer, whether out of choice or practical necessity (due to unsympathetic performers) remains to be addressed.

The non-harmonicity and awkwardness of performance evidently built a cultural barrier (something which Penderecki was not too fond of) and left the composer wondering where to turn.

A famous and often cited quote by Penderecki reads thus:

“The avant-garde gave one an illusion of universalism. The musical world of Stockhausen, Nono, Boulez and Cage was for us, the young - hemmed in by the aesthetics of socialist realism, then the official canon in our country - a liberation. It opened a new reality, a new vision of art and of the world. I was quick to realise however, that this novelty, this experimentation and formal speculation, is more destructive than constructive; I realised the Utopian quality of its Promethean tone. I was saved from the avant-garde snare of formalism by a return to tradition”³²

The tone of this quote seems to be one of sincere confession on his opinions of the avant-garde and at the time shows his faith in tradition as being a defining force in his stylistic growth. It seems that this realisation, about the uncertainties of the avant-garde, was a decisive factor and his labelling of the music as formalist shows a conscious awareness.

³¹Ibid.

³²Penderecki (1993) used by Tomaszewski, Mieczyslaw (2000). "Orchestral Works Vol 1", Liner Notes, Naxos CD, 8.554491, p. 2.

He even mentions the style of the 1950s as a form of political rebellion, which was one the main concerns of Polish artists at this time. Indeed, many composers were incredibly frustrated by the still present soviet occupation of their country and thought that by liberating people's minds they could initiate an artistic and social revolution.

A youthful intelligence and commitment to prove himself in the eyes of the establishment are likely reasons for his early compositional successes, and from the outside it certainly seems like populism was the primary cause of his change. The age of his *Dies Irae* is a long way off from his later works, which deal with themes far from the destruction and horror apparent in his earlier works.

For Penderecki the avant-garde and his meeting with it seems to have reached a peak of expressive ascent and plateau. Thus, Penderecki's style can be broadly seen, (at least in my eyes) as Post-modern, with indeed the modern searching at the end of the of the twentieth century and the destruction, persecution and indeed calming down of society. This, I believe is reflected in his music which turns later on to a more nineteenth century expression. Aspects of post modernism are reflected in his use of contemporary texts, native and foreign poetry, ideas, philosophies, expressive devices, instrumentation and development with older more stable romantic uses of harmony and extended chromaticism and subtle elements of pandiatonicism.

Górecki's path and opinions about his change are less clear. In works such as *Refrain*, he was to break from the rules of his dodecaphonic roots, and from the outset this is a more classical piece than its predecessors. Even if it contains related material to *Scontri*.³³ *Refrain* stands out from previous compositions. The use of divisi strings containing melodies that Adrian Thomas has cited as cantabile and containing a luminosity and combined with lines reminiscent of church chanting³⁴ is certainly a new development in his career and although there can still be seen a youthful intelligence here, the procedures of development and organisation are much more akin to his earlier works. Indeed, it would seem the work is riddled with palindromes.³⁵

In summary Thomas reviews the work as thus:

“In retrospect, *Refrain* appears to be a pivotal work, drawing from its predecessors and anticipating later compositions, sometimes at a remove of many years...broader patterns such as mirror patterns and refrains, sustained harmonic schemes, and slowly evolving melodic lines within the ambit of a minor third, along with familiar abrupt contrasts of texture and dynamics, are now thoroughly integrated as substantive structural components. Górecki had achieved in *Refrain* the individual and uncompromising balance between technique and expression for which he had been so diligently searching.”³⁶

³³Adrian Thomas, *Górecki, Oxford Studies of Composers*, (Oxford University Press, 1997). p. 52.

³⁴Adrian Thomas, *Górecki, Oxford Studies of Composers*, (Oxford University Press, 1997). p. 53.

³⁵Anna, Maslowiec, “The Utmost Economy of Musical Material.” Structural Elements in the Works of Górecki from *Refrain* (1965) to *Ad Matrem* (1971) Polish Musical Journal.

³⁶Adrian Thomas, (1997), p. 54.

He was to move further along this path with *Old Polish Music* (1969). Which introduces Polish melodies albeit in an entirely new context.

“It would soon become clear that there was an alternative Górecki at work in the 1960s. To be referring, however obliquely, to old musical traditions in Poland at this time was both unusual and, with regard to church music, something of a finger in the eye of the state authorities.”³⁷

This returning to old traditions is further enhanced by his work *Three Pieces in Old Style for string orchestra* (1963). The piece was composed in response to a jibe from the head of PWM that Górecki was not composing with tunes.

The work makes use of three melodies from very different sources: the first being a lamentation of the holy cross monastery, the second is a country dance in the aeolian mode and the third is attributed to a mid-sixteenth century royal wedding song and is in the dorian mode. Following this, Górecki's style was to become more rooted in the music that surrounded him and indeed many pieces after this time bear motifs or melodies attributed to Silesian folk song, particularly songs from the region of his youth.

It has been said many times the Penderecki was a more international or cosmopolitan composer compared to Górecki's native roots.

It is true that Górecki did not have the same cultural mind-set that Penderecki had and his appearances in public were rare, he was indeed more reclusive than his contemporary and preferred the company of locals rather than that of international composers and academics which seems more in tune with his rustic beginnings. Beginnings which were central to his stylistic growth in the 1960s.

³⁷Adrian Thomas, (1997), p. 58.

Thus we return to Górecki's quote from the cover page:

“I was born in Silesia...It is old Polish land. But there were always three cultures present: Polish, Czech, and German. The folk art, all the art, had no boundaries. These boundaries were supposed to exist, but they were shifted frequently to the right and to the left. But that did not mean that people started thinking differently.” Henryk Górecki (1997)

The folk music of the mountains and the chant that he heard in church are central to his outlook. His string quartets are often quite difficult listening, but in a way much different to his earlier work, as they demand much concentration and attention to minute detail. Long repeated passages and often bare accompaniment, to the unfamiliar listener can seem incredibly tedious. Although they feature elements of the Górale tunes which Górecki enjoyed so much.

If there was a work to frame the different (often disparate) aesthetics of his work, it would be his *Symphony Number 2 “Copernican”* (1972) who's almost apocalyptic, instrumental driven, first movement is balanced by a softer more drawn out vocally sustained second movement and shows Górecki's styles as if were two sides of the same coin. A work combining the main elements of each style.

Górecki's almost hermit³⁸ like position leant more to a style that was characterised by note repetitions and blocks of consonant against dissonant material in antithesis of the serial principle. However, his work should not be seen as minimalistic, but minimal in design and not a conscious use of basic musical components like in the New York School of Minimalism, but more of a attempt at soundscaping and meditation of design akin to Penderecki's own style.

³⁸He has described himself as a recluse.

As, perhaps, a paring down of an early violent aesthetic. Of course, Górecki's success with his *Third Symphony* "*Symphony of Sorrowful Songs*" which features a return to the medieval lament, a WWII Gestapo cell inscription, and a song from the town of Opole, can be seen as his first truly internationally recognisable achievement, but it is unfair to determine his style and indeed his stylistic evolution (as many writers often do) solely on this work. Neoromantic sonorism is central to his evolution, and after *Refrain* he went back to the drawing board so to speak, poor health also contributed to this and there were no works written between 1965 and 1967.

Górecki's more reclusive character suited a stylistic move and his success much later on in his career with the sales of a CD of *Third Symphony* in 1992 did much to drive him deeper into the cultural background, although he did supervise recordings with Dawn Upshaw and attended some performances of his work. His change to a less avant-garde style needs to be handled with care.

Last November Górecki died at the age of 77 and left an incredibly interesting catalogue of works behind, and not least the premier of his *Symphony Number 4* which has yet to be performed in public.

He was a very private man, and this was certainly shown in his later works.

Adrian Thomas writes on Górecki's death.

"My most abiding memory of him was being with him in the Tatra mountains. There he was in his element, hiking and talking to craftsmen and farmers. It seemed to me that he, like Karol Szymanowski before him, was never happier than in the company of Tatra musicians, from the highland people known as Górale, occasionally joining in on the fiddle."³⁹

³⁹Adrian Thomas, Obituary for The Guardian Newspaper, 25 November, 2010, <<http://www.guardian.co.uk/music/2010/nov/25/henryk-gorecki-obituary-appreciation>>, [Accessed 30 April, 2011].

In relation to the differences between Górecki and Penderecki Bernard Jacobson has compared Penderecki's aesthetic and psychology of being more akin to Sigmund Freud and Górecki's being more like Carl Jung.⁴⁰ Thus we can see Górecki as being more fascinated with extremes in both dynamics and tempo, and Penderecki's focus, on more subtle dramatic processes and mental and dramatic subject matter seems fundamentally important to his aesthetic and reception. Penderecki's looking outside of himself has often led to many incidents of trial and error and indeed a self-questioning and a questioning the world around him is evident in his work. Górecki's journey is more personal, as if composition to him was his way of reconciling himself with the world or with his God. He was not simply a product of his environment or faith but his attitude to it influenced his music to a significant degree.

6. Polish music now, twenty years on: a multifaceted being

Polish music now is a strong cultural force and although the popularity of the Warsaw Autumn has been eclipsed by other festivals around Europe, it still seems to be an important institution of Poland music. Younger composers such as Paweł Strzelecki⁴¹, Paweł Łukaszewski known for his choral music and artists and composers such as Jarek Kordaczuk have contributed to a dynamic twenty-first century voice and represent the legacy of conflicting neoclassical, modernist, neoromantic, jazz, electronic, multimedia, and sound art that form part of the aesthetic of Polish composers today. The influence of IRCAM in the training of

⁴⁰ Bernard Jacobson, *A Polish Renaissance*, (London: Phaidon Press, 1996), p. 200.

⁴¹Also a musicologist and author of *Nowy romantyzm w twórczości kompozytorów polskich po roku 1975*, (*Neoromanticism in the works of Polish composers after 1975*).

composers such as Joanna Bruzdowicz is an important factor which helped electronic music take hold in Poland. With only funding limitations and the place of culture and modernism in contemporary Poland have inhibited Polish cultural growth in the twenty-first century.

After the fall of the Iron curtain, Poland, like most former Soviet states found it difficult to adapt to the practise of capitalism and the idea of a free market economy. In fact, many Poles have cited the economic development of their country as being “ten years behind” most of their Western counterparts. The feelings of belonging and integration are strong in twenty-first century Europe and Polish music has grown and adapted since the cold war, although there are still many controversies and contradictions that dominate Polish news and politics today.

The composer Leoncjusz Ciuciura has written in his letter at the end of the twentieth century as an introduction to his aesthetic, but also as an epilogue to the twentieth century which had been the most trying in Polish cultural history.

“Dear Friend,

The quick, dynamic changes and transformations which Poland, Europe and our whole contemporary World undergoes are the challenge also for us the people of art. We have to stop to be witnesses and passive observers covered with the shield of aestheticism. We must turn to a new dynamic arising reality and enter its current, bravely facing its new problems, conflicts and threats. ...It seems true to be true that at the end of the XX century our present situation, not only in Poland and Europe, but also over the world is much more advantageous. The political-social evolution has enabled the arising of proper conditions and climate for many new favourable activities, of which the base is determined by new trends, in this among others, the trend to integration in all fields. The contemporary World wants to integrate, and it is necessary for it to survive. It is obvious to me, as a composer, that this union and supplement cannot

and should not take place in an economical sphere but also in a cultural one. And this sphere was, is and should always be in our hands – the hands of artists...⁴²

Polish music has always been a complicated phenomenon, enhanced by an incredibly turbulent twentieth century. It is the Polish resolve that has created some of the most startlingly original compositions of this era.

Composers such as Henryk Górecki and Krzysztof Penderecki began their careers and experimented in a period of political freedom and developed their styles in pursuit of a unified aesthetic. They developed idiosyncratic styles throughout their careers which helped to further the progress of Polish music. Scholars have dismissed their stylistic changes as turning their backs on their avant-garde sonorist roots. But I argue that it was precisely these roots and their environment that helped to shape their music and assert their cultural stamp on the music of the twentieth century.

Ben Mc Hugh

Dublin, Ireland 2011

⁴²Ciuiura, Leoncjusz, Introduction Letter to performers for *Spiral Form* an international collaborative performance project, Edition, 20. March 1997.

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